

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICE OF ELECTRONIC MEDICAL RECORDS SYSTEMS BY HEALTH INFORMATION PROFESSIONALS IN SELECTED MEDICAL CENTRES IN ABUJA.

By

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ABSTRACT

Successful implementation of EMRs programme no doubt, depends a lot on adequate awareness, knowledge, positive attitude and best practices of all personnel involved in the system. In this study, a sample of 50(fifty) health Information Management (HIM) professionals were drawn from HIM population of 97 (Ninety-seven) under the FCT HHSS, using proportional allocation technique. Their knowledge attitude and practice towards the EMRs programme were assessed using the KAP survey, Findings, show that HIM professionals of FCT HHSS are adequately aware and also have very good knowledge of the EMR system in FCT, Abuja. They generally exhibit positive attitude towards the programme but are however in general, not able to perform most of the core EMRs functions like trend Analyses. It is recommended that amongst others, for data collection and analyses to be very effective, there should be training and retraining programs for the HIM professionals in the hospitals. This will hopefully, improve their computational and mathematical skills thus enabling them perform all core functions of the EMRs practices.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Electronic Medical Record

1. INTRODUCTION

The healthcare industry has made significant investments in technology for diagnostic, clinical and treatment purposes though its adoption has been slow in developing countries. Until recently, only

few healthcare facilities have made the investments needed for the acceptance and use of electronic medical records which has allowed medical practices to replace traditional patient charts with computerized system (Aishwarya, 2015). A medical record is a confidential record that is kept for each patient by a healthcare professional or organization. Traditionally, each healthcare provider involved in a patient's care has kept an independent record, usually paper based. Given the changes in technology particularly the move to computerized information storage, make it possible to store the entire medical record, or any part of it, on computer. To make such a change involves significant investment in both equipment and staff, but the benefits can far outweigh the costs. Electronic records greatly extend the concept of the medical record, and enable many functions that are otherwise quite impossible.

The Electronic Medical Record system stores physicians' notes, x-rays, prescriptions, and other medical information in electronic format rather than paper files thus make searching for, retrieving, and sharing patient data easier and more efficient. As opined by Al Farsi, & West, (2006), hospital Information System (HIS) and Electronic Medical Record (EMR) are considered necessary for the efficient delivery of high-quality care, proper management of patients and to decrease in medical errors in healthcare delivery. Since EMR system has the potential to improve the quality and effectiveness of the healthcare delivery. Alquraini et al (2007) reported that many healthcare providing organizations in developed countries have invested in its development and use while et al (2010) reported that in many developing countries the use of EMR system is not wide spread.

According to Aydin (2009), EMR implementation leads to improvement in quality of healthcare, decreased time spent on paperwork, increased patient satisfaction, and financial savings. It is also believed to eliminates the need for handwritten records, thus reducing time spent on record storage, which in turn results in reduced patient waiting time (Baron et al, 2005). Similarly, tracking time of previous records is also reduced by accessing the computerized medical records through the computerized central system (Blank et al, 2013) as the EMR system ensures high-quality documentation and easy to retrieval of data system than the paper-based medical record system. Other benefits include accurate medication lists, readable notes and prescriptions and immediately available charts Brumini, et al (2005).

EMR systems are increasingly being utilized and automated in healthcare systems to improve effectiveness, timeliness, efficiency, quality of healthcare, data management, and decision-making. Nevertheless, EMR system implementations has faced confrontations from users even in the technically equipped healthcare working setups (David, 2010). WHO (2016) indicated financial, technical, and infrastructural barriers as the commonest which are directly related to healthcare professionals' unwillingness to use EMR. Other factors that affected the willingness to use EMR systems by healthcare experts include system users, facility setups, availability of skilled human capital, information and resource availability, training, computer literacy, English language proficiency, educational status, and knowledge of EMR (David, 2006).

Besides health care providers, Electronic Medical Record is an important factor in patient satisfaction. A significant percentage of patients take Electronic Medical Record access into consideration when choosing a healthcare provider. Patients are more satisfied and feel a stronger loyalty with their doctors. EMR's usage improves physician-patient relationship. They express higher satisfaction across different dimensions of care, such as

higher confidence in the quality of healthcare they receive from Electronic Medical Record Users. They also believe they receive better quality care. Patients who prefer their doctor to use an electronic chart cited numerous reasons including: access to medical records; accuracy/better record keeping; and coordination of care and information sharing. They quoted that electronic medical records are more accurate than paper charts. Thus, those who adopt Electronic Medical Record System are at a competitive advantage since it yields dividends beyond the expected operational efficiencies- namely it enhances patient satisfaction and loyalty as opined by David, (2006).

Ford et' al (2006) thus averred that Electronic Medical Record (EMR) System has great potential to transform healthcare practice, including the enhancement of healthcare delivery and facilitation of decision-making processes. In spite of challenges facing the developing world such as lack of human expertise and financial resource, most studies have shown how feasible it could be to design and implement an EMR system that fits into the environment

Despite these advantages, implementation of Electronic Medical Record Systems may be resisted if users are not satisfied. Physicians and nurses have concerns about security and confidentiality, time incurred by Electronic Medical Record use, or negative impacts on the quality of patient care (Burnum,1989). In spite of the reluctance Electronic Medical Record ultimately contributes to development of healthcare delivery.

The successful implementation of an electronic medical record (EMR) system depends on the acceptance of the system by the user who puts it into practice. Therefore, understanding medical professionals' attitudes toward the use of EMRs is important for a successful implementation of the system. This study examined the attitude of medical professionals toward the use of EMRs by drawing from the theory of innovation diffusion and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). First, we identified the characteristics of EMRs and examined their impact on perceived usefulness, which together with perceived ease of use in turn influences attitude toward using EMR. Second, we examine the moderating effects of self-image between the key constructs of the TAM. To examine our research model, survey data from physicians and nurses from different hospitals were collected and analyzed using confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling techniques.

Implementing an electronic health record (EHR) can be a difficult task to take on and planning the process is of utmost importance to minimize errors. Evaluating the selection criteria and implementation plan of an EHR system, intending interoperability, confidentiality, availability, and integrity of the patient health information data, while ensuring timely, accurate, and regulatory compliant generation of reports is a critical task.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite all the benefits of implementing Electronic Medical Record which are providing accurate, up to date and complete information about patients at the point of care, Enabling quick access to patients records for more coordinated, efficient care, securely sharing electronic information with patients and other, improving patient and provider interaction and communication, as well as health care convenience that has being well documented, some hospitals in Nigeria are yet to implement this system. However, some hospitals that have implemented it suddenly stop using the system. It is in this light that this project aimed to assess how Knowledge, attitude affect the

practice of EMR. This research aims to look into the loopholes and make an effective recommendation to avoid failure in any future project.

1.2 Aims & Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to assess the knowledge, attitude and, practice of electronic medical records system usage in healthcare delivery at Abuja District Hospitals FCT. The objectives are to;

- i. Find out the reasons why some hospitals do not use Electronic Medical Records systems in Abuja.
- ii. Identify factors that had led to the discontinuation of Electronic Medical Records systems in hospitals in Abuja.
- iii. Examine the type of Electronic Medical Records systems available in Abuja FMC hospitals.
- iv. Find out if EMR knowledge affects Electronic Medical Records systems deployment.
- v. Examine how attitude of staff in records serve as deterrent to operationalizing EMR system in their hospital in Abuja.
- vi. Investigate the relationship between staff attitude to Electronic Medical Records systems and its implementation in each of the hospital in Abuja.
- vii. Investigate the relationship between staff knowledge of Electronic Medical Records systems and its implementation in each of hospital in Abuja.
- viii. Investigate the combined influence of staff knowledge, attitude and implementation of Electronic Medical Records systems in hospital in Abuja

1.3 Research Questions

- i. What are the reasons why some medical centers don't use EMR system?
- ii. What are the factors that has led to the discontinuation of use of EMR system at some hospitals?
- iii. What are the type of EMR system available to each hospital?
- iv. How does EMR knowledge affect EMR system implementation?
- v. How does attitude of staff in Records serves as deterrent to operationalizing EMR system in the hospitals

1.4 Hypothesis

H₀¹ There is no significant relationship between staff attitude to EMR and its implementation in the selected hospitals in Abuja

H₀² There is no significant relationship between staff knowledge of EMR and its implementation in the selected hospitals in Abuja

1.5 Scope of the study

This project is on the knowledge, attitude and practice of EMR system usage in healthcare delivery, using some selected hospitals in Abuja, which are: Nyanya General Hospital, Maitama District Hospital, Asokoro District Hospital, Wuse District Hospital, Gwarimpa District Hospital, Kubwa General Hospital, Bwari General Hospital, Karchi General Hospital, Kuje General Hospital, Robochi General Hospital, Kwali General Hospital and Dutse District Hospital, whereby creating an effective communication between patients and health provider which will eradicate duplication

of patient data, time wastage involved in retrieval of patient information. Also, it will provide literature on how accessibility of patients' health record in a systematic way by providing adequate security measures to safe guard their privacy.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study seeks to shed light on the knowledge, Attitude and practice of electronic medical record usage in healthcare delivery. To this end, the findings and recommendations from this study will add to the existing knowledge already established in the field of electronic records management. It will help to create the basis of decision making for the various stakeholders involved in the health care system especially in Abuja District Hospital. The study will help the hospital management of Federal capital territory, Abuja to make efficient planning in the implementation of Electronic medical record. This study will benefit the management of FCT in helping her identify the present loopholes in the EMR system of its hospital, and also help her to appreciate the challenges associated with records management and how to address these teeming challenges to improve quality healthcare delivery.

Another significance of this study is its ability to provide useful information on EMR to health students and the general public. Furthermore, the study will help reveal the need for good records management for effective planning of Abuja District Hospitals to ensure rapid growth and development.

Lastly, this study will help in providing the government and health policy decision makers with established and accurate data for effective policy formulation and regulation.

2. METHODOLOGY

This project is on the knowledge, attitude and practice of EMR system in healthcare delivery, using some selected hospitals in Abuja; Nyanya General Hospital, Maitama District Hospital, Asokoro District Hospital, Wuse District Hospital, Gwarimpa District Hospital, Kubwa General Hospital, Bwari General Hospital, Karchi General Hospital, Kuje General Hospital, Robochi General Hospital, Kwali General Hospital and Dutse District Hospital,

2.1 Research Design

The design used for study was descriptive survey design. It was chosen because it helps to gather adequate information concerning the research problem as at the time of research and to ascertain knowledge, attitude and practice of electronic medical records system usage in the health care facilities of FCT, Abuja.

2.2 Study Population

The study population includes ninety-seven (97) Health information management professionals in the health care facilities of FCT, Abuja.

2.3. Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Total enumeration was used for the study. This is because the population of study (which is the HIM professionals in FMC Abuja) was low.

Table 1: Number of HIM professionals in each facility

S/NO	Name of facility (h)	No. of HIM Professionals (Nh)	Number of Questionnaire Returned
1	Nyanaya General hospital	9	4
2	Maitama District Hospital	10	5
3	Asokoro District Hospital	17	9
4	Wuse District Hospital	15	8
5	Gwarimpa District Hospital	9	4
6	Kubwa General hospital	8	4
7	Bwari General hospital	8	4
8	Karchi General hospital	7	4
9	Kuje General hospital	5	3
10	Robochi General hospital	3	2
11	Kwali General hospital	2	1
12	Dutse District Hospital	4	2
Total	12	97	50

2.4 Description of Research instrument

Data were collected using questionnaires and Reports of the FCTA Health and human services secretariat. Questionnaire is a document containing a set of questions expected to be responded to, by the Respondents which will lead to data collection in research. The questionnaire was preferred for this research due to its flexibility, affordability and ease of administration. It was suitable because it allowed the researcher to reach out to the sample within a limited time period. It also ensured confidentiality, and thus it enabled the researcher to gather more candid and objective data. The type of questionnaire made use of here is the self-administered, structured Questionnaire. This is in cognizance of the level of the academic qualification and work experience of the population under study.

The Reports refers to FCTA Health & Human resources secretariat Annual reports from which data and information relevant to the study were extracted.

2.5 Reliability and Validity of the Research Instrument.

The reliability and Validity of this report rest completely outside the control of the researcher, but within that of FCT HHSS. Where interviews were needed it only served for clarification purpose and follow-up. In fact, Borge et al (1993) indicated that questionnaires are often used to collect basic descriptive information from a large sample, while interviews are used to follow-up questionnaires. The three (3) instruments adopted here:

Questionnaires, interview and the Reports, were used in the study for the purpose of triangulation and confirming information collected from various sources. The researcher had hoped that, by adopting these methods, Sampling errors due to bias might be adequately minimized.

2.6 Data Collection Techniques

A Structured Questionnaire were prepared and administered to only HIM professionals in each of the twelve (12) hospitals in a proportional allocation technique. Part of which were completed and

returned, representing 52% returns. All of them were equally usable as there were no errors in any one of them.

2.7 Method of Data of Analysis

Methods of descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data obtained through the questionnaires. The use of Descriptive statistics was considered appropriate for this research because it involved the Description, Tabulation, Calculations, Analysis and Interpretation of the variables considered in this study. Basic statistical techniques were used to analyze various items of the Questionnaires and the Reports.

These include: Average (means), percentages, Frequencies, and Tools. The choice of these techniques was informed because they easily communicate results of research findings to majority of readers, (Prabhakara,2010).

2.8 Ethical Consideration

Participants were fully briefed about the study purpose and the procedures for data collection in clear language that they could understand. All the data collected was anonymised to ensure that participants' identities were protected.

3 PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

Tables and charts would be used to present findings. Data collected would be analyzed according to the nature of responses.

3.1 Bio-Data Analysis of Respondents

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents by Gender

S/N	Name of Facility	No. of HIM Profession	Returned Questionnaire by Respondents	Male Resp. (M.R.)	Female Resp. (F.R.)	% M.R	% F.R
	Nyanya GH	9	4	1	3	25	75
	Maitama DH	10	5	2	3	40	60
	Asokoro DH	17	9	4	5	44	56
	Wuse DH	15	8	3	5	38	62
	Gwarinpa DH	9	4	1	3	25	75
	Kubwa GH	8	4	1	2	50	50
	Bwari GH	8	4	1	3	25	75
	Karchi GH	7	4	1	3	25	75

	Kuje GH	5	3	0	3	0	100
	Abaji GH	4	2	0	2	0	100
	Robochi GH	3	2	1	1	50	50
	Kwali GH	2	1	0	1	0	100
Total	12	97	50	16	34		
				32%	64%		

Table 2 above revealed that, of the 4 Respondents in Nyanya General Hospital, as high as 3 of them were female while I was male officer constituting only %25 of the respondents in hospital. Also 75% respondents in each of Gwarinpa, Bwari, Karshi General Hospitals respectively, are all females. However, at Maitama District Hospital, 60% of the respondents were female while 40% were male interestingly, while all the respondents in Kuje and Abaji were all females, there were equal male and female Respondents in Kubwa and Robochi General Hospitals; and 38% Male and 62% female Respondents at Wuse District Hospital. The researcher did not identify any possible implication of this composition on the integrity of the data obtained from them.

Table 3: Socio demographic characteristics of the respondents

Characteristics	Frequency (50)	Percentage (100%)
Age		
18-25	40	88.5
26-40	7	5.5
41-55	3	2.1
Sex		
Female	32	70.1
Male	18	15.0
Religion		
Christian	27	56.7
Islam	23	42.5
Traditional	0	0.8
Marital status		
Single	20	38.5
Married	30	62.5
Ethnicity		
Yoruba	10	10.0
Igbo	6	4.0
Hausa	34	65

Qualification		
OND	18	35
HND	5	5
R.N	2	2.0
PHD	1	0.5
BSC	22	40.0
MSC	2	0.5
Profession		
Doctor	12	15.0
Nursing	5	8.0
Medical Record Officer	21	30.0
NHIS staff	6	9.0
Pharmacy	6	9.0
Department		
CHOP	4	7.5
GOP	8	15.9
Laboratory	6	10
MOP	5	7.5
Nursing	3	2.5
O&G	3	6.6
Pharmacy	4	11.6
Record	8	15.0
SOP	5	6.7
NHIS	4	16.7

Table 3 above showed socio-demographic characteristics of respondents who took part in this research. Respondents (88%) aged 26-40 were more than those in other age groups while the least number of respondents (5%) were those aged 41-55 years; there were equal gender proportion, females (70%) and males (15%) in the study. The most prevalent religion was Christianity (56.7%), followed by Islam (42.5%) and traditional religion (0.8%). Marital status of respondents showed that there were more single respondents (38.5%) than (62.5%) married. More respondents were Hausa (65.5%) than any other ethnic group. Most respondents (23.3%) were NHIS staff and most of the respondents (32.5%) were BSC holder while (40.7%) of respondents were from the NHIS department.

Table 4: Reasons for using Electronic Medical Records system

Characteristic	Frequency (50)	Percentage (100%)
EMR provide easy access to patient information.	50	100
Agree	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Undecided		

EMR have the ability to help identify high risk area		
Agree	40	80
Disagree	5	10
Undecided	5	10
EMR system are sufficient for the clinical documentation and workflow		
Agree	50	100
Disagree	0	0
Undecided	0	0
EMR help in clinical decision making, planning for outbreaks and identifying transmission processes		
Agree	50	100
Disagree	0	0
Undecided	0	0
EMR enables easy billing and reimbursement processes		
Agree	50	100
Disagree	0	0
Undecided	0	0
EMR helps to reduce operational cost such as transcription services and overtime labor expenses		
Agree	46	95.0
Disagree	2	5.0
Undecided	2	5.0
EMR improve result management and patient care with a reduction in errors within the medical practices		
Agree	50	100
Disagree	0	0
Undecided	0	0

Table 4 showed the reasons for the use of electronic medical records at the health facility in which all respondent responded well. All the respondents (100%) agreed that EMR provide easy access to patient information; more than half of the respondents (80.7%) agreed to EMR having the ability to help identify high risk area, while (100.5%) disagreed, and (0.8%) are indecisive; Majority (100.2%) agreed that EMR system are sufficient for clinical documentation and workflow, while(0.8%) disagreed; Most (100.2%) respondents agreed that EMR help in clinical decision making, planning for outbreaks and identifying transmission of diseases, while (0%) disagreed and (0.5%) are indecisive; Respondent agreed and disagreed (96.7%), (3.3%) respectively on the question which says EMR enables easy billing and reimbursement process; Majority (95.0%) agreed that EMR helps to reduce operational cost such as transcription services and overtime labor

expenses, while (5.0%) disagreed; Almost all (100.%) of the respondent said EMR improves result management and patient care with reduction in errors within the medical practices.

Table 5: Factors that led to the discontinuation of use of electronic medical records

Characteristic	Frequency (50)	(100%)
Lack of coordination and effective interoperation of EMR system within all departments in the hospital. Agree Disagree Undecided	50 0 0	100 0 0
Inconsistent power supplies Agree Disagree Undecided	48 2 0	85.8 4 0
Healthcare workers are inadequately trained on how to use the EMR system Agree Disagree Undecided	50 0 0	100 0 0
Lack of skilled manpower Agree Disagree Undecided	40 8 2	80 16 4.0
High cost of maintaining the EMR system Agree Disagree Undecided	50 0 0	100 0 0
Lack of technical support Agree Disagree Undecided	45 5 6	90 8 2.0
Internet connection problem Agree Disagree Undecided	50 0 0	100 0 0
Healthcare worker are not willing to use EMR system Agree Disagree Undecided	- 40 10	- 90.0 10.0

Table 5 showed the responds of the respondent on the challenges that led to the discontinuation of the use of electronic medical records reasons. Almost all the respondents (100%) agreed that lack of coordination and effective interoperation of the EMR system within all departments in the hospital while (0.8)disagreed; majority (85.8%) agreed to inconsistent power supplies, while (14.2%) disagreed; Majority (90.0%) agreed that healthcare workers are inadequately trained on how to use the EMR system, while(12.5%) disagreed and (2.5%) indecisive; Most (80.5%) respondents that lack of skilled manpower, while (16.5%) respondent disagree and (5.0%) are indecisive; Respondent agreed and disagreed (100%) respectively on the high cost of maintaining the EMR system; Majority (90.5%) agreed that lack of technical support, while (8.5%) disagreed and (2.0%) are indecisive; Almost all (100.%) of the respondent said internet connection problem while the remaining (0%)percent disagreed; Most (90.0%) respond that healthcare workers are not willing to use the EMR systems, and (10%) respondent disagreed.

Table 6: Years of working experience of respondents

S/N	YEARS IN SERVICE	N=50	N%
1.	1 – 2 YRS	7	14%
2.	3 – 4 YRS	11	22%
3.	5 – 6 YRS	23	46%
4.	7 – 8 YRS	8	16%
5.	& Above	1	2%

Fig. 1 Years of working experience of the respondents in pie chart

From table 6 and Fig. 1, 14% of the respondents have worked in their respective facility for a period of between 1 and 2 while 23 of them, representing 46% have worked for between 5-6 years, 8 of them have worked for between 7-8 years while only 1 respondent have worked for more than 9 years. The above data suggest that a majority of the respondents have substantial level of experience in their given responsibilities in the EMR system programme as HIM professional.

3.2 Knowledge of the EMR system by the HIM professionals

Table 7: Number of HIM professional who are aware of the existence of the system in their facilities

Knowledge of the EMR system by the HIM professional	50	N %
Awareness of the EMR system in your facility:		
Yes	48	96%
No	2	4%

Table 5 show that as much as 48 of the 50 respondents affirm that they were aware of them of the existence of the EMR system in their respective healthcare facilities representing a whopping 96%, while only 2 of them claimed they were not aware of such, they represent only 4% of the

respondents; This is assumed to be a good report in that it hope to give results adequate enough for local generalization of their awareness of the existence of the EMR system at the FCT secondary healthcare facilities.

3.3 Attitude of respondents towards the EMR system.

This section dealt with the attitudinal and pre-disposition of the respondent HIM professionals towards the EMR system, measuring attitudes is a part of the standard KAP survey questionnaire administered to the respondent, the section analyzed the personnel responses which indicated their prevailing tendencies to respond favorably or unfavorable or unfavorably to the EMR system.

Table 8: Attitude of Respondents towards the EMR system

	Attitude of Respondents towards the EMR system	50	n%
i.	Attach great importance to the EMR system	5	10
ii.	EMR system is a programme to be embraced & encouraged	16	32
iii.	Optimistic that EMR system would achieve its stated aims & objectives in Abuja	23	46
iv.	Believe in the EMR system implementation	43	86
v.	Do not believe in the EMR system programme	1	2
vi.	Indifference	4	8
vii.	No response	4	8

Table 8 provides great insight into the attitude of the respondent HIM professional towards the electronic medical Record system programme. The diagrams show that only (5) 10% of the respondents said they attach great importance to the EMR system; (16) 32% feel that the EMRs is a programme that should embraced & encouraged; (23) 46% of them are optimistic that EMRs would achieve its stated aims and objective in Abuja.

Fig. 2: Attitudes of respondents towards the EMR system.

While almost all the respondents i.e. (43) 86% believe in the programme only (1) 2% them do not believe in the programme. However, (2) 4% respondents did not respond to the issue and (4) 8% claimed indifferent to the EMR system programme.

The result on the knowledge, attitude and practice of using an electronic medical record in first instances revealed that all the respondents agreed that EMR provide easy access to patient information which agrees with the study carried out by Amatayakul, (2007) where he stated that EMR support better health care by improving all aspects of patient care, including safety, effectiveness, patient centeredness, communication, education, timeliness, efficiency and equity. More than half of the respondents accept that EMR have the ability to help identify high risk area. Majority of the respondent accepted that EMR system is sufficient for clinical documentation and workflow. Most of the respondents revealed that EMR help in clinical decision making, planning for outbreaks and identifying transmission of diseases. Almost all respondent accepted that EMR enables easy billing and reimbursement process. Majority of the respondent revealed that EMR helps to reduce operational cost such as transcription services and overtime labor expenses. This corroborate the study carried out by Amatayakul, (2007) which says that EMR enables improved efficiencies and lower health care costs by promoting preventive medicine and improved coordination of health care services as well as reducing waste and redundant test Almost the entire respondent said EMR improves result management and patient care with reduction in errors within the medical practices.

Results of the study showed that compatibility, security and accuracy have a positive effect on perceived usefulness, but reliability had no significant effect on perceived usefulness. Moreover, self-image acted as a moderating variable between the relationships between perceived ease of use and attitude and between perceived usefulness and attitude toward the use of EMR.

4 DISCUSSION

The study examined the influence of knowledge, attitudes and practice of Electronic medical records system usage in healthcare delivery using twelve (12) hospitals (secondary healthcare) FCT, Abuja. This chapter provides a summary of the findings and draw conclusions from the findings.

This study is carried out to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practice of Electronic medical records system usage in healthcare delivery using twelve (12) hospitals (secondary healthcare) FCT, Abuja as a case study. A descriptive design was adopted and two (2) specific objectives were developed to carry out the study. Purposive and Convenience sampling technique were used to select departments and respondents that participated in the study. A total number of 97 healthcare workers participated in the study. The data collected from the questionnaire were collated, entered into SPSS version 21 and analyzed using frequency and percentage.

Findings on the reason why twelve (12) hospitals (secondary healthcare) FCT, Abuja was using electronic medical record in first instances revealed that all the respondents agreed that EMR provide easy access to patient information. More than half of the respondents agreed that EMR have the ability to help identify high risk area. Majority of the respondent accepted that EMR system is sufficient for clinical documentation and workflow. Most of the respondents revealed that EMR help in clinical decision making, planning for outbreaks and identifying transmission of diseases. Almost all respondent accepted that EMR enables easy billing and reimbursement process. Majority of the respondent revealed that EMR helps to reduce operational cost such as transcription services and overtime labor expenses. Almost all the respondent said EMR improves result management and patient care with reduction in errors within the medical practices.

There is adequate awareness by the HIM professional, of the existence of the EMR system in their respective hospitals, they can identify the various EMRs tools and they have adequate knowledge of what each is meant for, FCT HIM professionals know the public health relevance and uses of the EMRs Records and are able to state many of them.

However, despite their strong believe in the EMR system, they do not attach great importance to it. They do not show sufficient strong or positive attitudinal disposition to the EMR system. They may not be unconnected with the work load of the Medical Records department as a result of the limited number of qualified HIM professionals in the FCT health & Human Services Secretariat.

Lastly, the findings on the knowledge, attitudes and practice of the use of electronic medical records revealed that majority of the respondents agreed that lack of coordination and effective interoperation of the EMR system within all departments in the hospital, inconsistent power supply and internet connection problem led to the discontinuation of EMR. Majority of the respondents accepted that lack of technical support and inadequate training of healthcare workers on how to use the EMR system and lack of skilled manpower contributed to the discontinuation of EMR. Also, majority of the respondents revealed that the high cost of maintaining the EMR system led to the discontinuation of EMR. Most respondents also responded that healthcare workers are not willing to use the EMR systems.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Conclusively, the reason why twelve (12) hospitals (secondary healthcare) FCT, Abuja was using electronic medical record in first instances was provision of easy access to patient information,

ability to help identify high risk area, sufficient for clinical documentation and workflow, clinical decision making, planning for outbreaks and identifying transmission of diseases, easy billing and reimbursement process, reduction in operational cost such as transcription services and overtime labor expenses and result management and patient care with reduction in errors within the medical practices. The challenges that led to the discontinuation of the use of electronic medical records were lack of coordination and effective interoperation of the EMR system within all departments in the hospital, inconsistent power supply, internet connection problem, lack of technical support, inadequate training of healthcare workers on how to use the EMR system, lack of skilled manpower, high cost of maintaining the EMR system and healthcare workers unwillingness to use the EMR systems.

5.1 Recommendations

The production of a project work requires some recommendations to be given. Base on the problems being identified in this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The hospital management must ensure that well design electronic medical records system that enables coordination and interoperability within all departments in the hospital is implemented
2. Adequate training in terms of seminars and workshops should be conducted in order to ensure that each health worker have better understanding on the use of electronic medical record system.
3. The hospital management must ensure good internet services in order to prevent network fluctuation.
4. The hospital management should also put into consideration all means of stable power supply at point of implementation.
5. There should be regular awareness information, education and communication program concerning the EMRs programme and its importance to the public, for health-care facility workers particularly the HIM professional at the FCT General or District hospital and on a regular basis too. This will help them appreciate the importance of the system and thus improve their general attitude towards it.
6. For data collection and analyses to be effective, there should be training and retraining programs for the HIM professionals in the hospitals. This will hopefully improve their computational and mathematical skill thus enabling them perform all core functions of the EMRs practices.
7. The staff strength of the HIM professional in the FCT HHSS, should urgently be increased to a level co-mensurate with the very crucial and important services they render to the public. This will substantially reduce their work load to a bearable minimum and enable them devote the necessary time to the EMRs functions.
8. For the EMR system to continue to be functional and effective there must be consent collaboration among communities, health facilities; the public health community and other agencies. This will definitely enhance opportunity for disease prevention and control. A close collaboration is essential for effective use of the EMRs for the proper collection of data and for the implementation of relevant actions, both public health and private healthcare organizations can benefits by sharing data and working together.

5.2 Limitations of Study

The study was carried out only on HIM professionals currently on the employment of the FCT Health & Human services secretariat and deployed to each of the twelve (12) hospitals controlled and managed by the Hospital management Board (HMB). It neither included Non-HIM professionals working in the HIM department nor other healthcare professionals in the hospitals who are equally involved in the EMR system. As a result, it may not be perfect for complete generalization.

Secondly, there are limited regional and national literatures on the subject matter.

Hence, it was difficult to sufficiently compare results of this work with those previous works done in Nigeria and the sub-Saharan Africa.

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